

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this research work on **Health Seeking Behaviour among Medical Students in the University of Uyo, Nigeria** was carried out by;

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DEDICATION

This work is dedicated first to God for the inspiration and strength to carry out this research. We also dedicate this to our parents/guardian who have supported us financially and also showed us unconditional love and support. Our dedication also goes to every medical student around the world especially in Nigeria going through rigorous medical training. Finally, we dedicate it to all our teachers who have guided us thus far.

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SUMMARY

BACKGROUND

Health Seeking Behaviour has been instrumental in explaining how people respond to their illness and why they make certain choices as related to their health. Health seeking behaviour of health professionals may have been imbibed at an early stage of medical training. Thus, this study determined the health seeking behaviour of medical students in the University of Uyo and the factors responsible for these behaviours.

METHOD

The study was a cross-sectional institutional-based study. Study tool was a semi-structured self-administered questionnaire. Statistical analysis was done using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences SPSS version 26. Level of significance for all statistical test was set at 0.05.

RESULT

Two hundred and sixty-two respondents participated, out of which 59.2% of respondents were males. Two hundred and sixteen (82.4%) were less than 25 years of age. The majority (60.7%) were in their clinical level of medical training. The majority 92.4% experienced illness symptoms in the last 6 months. The commonest symptoms were headache (69.1%) followed by fever (66.4%) and low mood/depression (45.4%). The commonest illness response was going to the pharmacy (50.8%) followed by resting and doing nothing (23.6%), and consulting a colleague (9.8%). Only 21 (8.5%) visited the hospital at once. Taking herbal medication ($p=0.029$) and consulting a colleague ($p=0.028$) was commoner among females, while going to the pharmacy ($p=0.005$) was commoner among males. Clinical level was associated with visiting the pharmacy ($p=0.031$). Perceived severity of illness ($p<0.001$), past experience ($p<0.001$), efficiency ($p=0.001$), cost ($p=0.002$), ease of access ($p=0.018$), trust ($p<0.001$) and confidentiality ($p=0.013$) were reasons associated with various health seeking behaviours.

CONCLUSION

Low mood/depression was unusually higher compared to previous studies. Almost a quarter of medical students took no action for their symptoms. Interestingly, few medical students found herbal medicine to be more effective than orthodox care. There should more health education and counselling opportunities for medical students on the negative effects of poor health seeking behaviour.

**HEALTH SEEKING BEHAVIOUR AMONG MEDICAL
STUDENTS IN THE UNIVERSITY OF UYO, NIGERIA.**

CHAPTER 1 - INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND

Health seeking behaviour has been described as any action or inaction by an individual who perceives himself or herself as ill or having a health problem, with the purpose of finding an appropriate remedy¹. It is also known as illness behaviour or care seeking behaviour of any individual who is otherwise unhealthy, with the ultimate goal of finding an individual-based subjective solution to the health problem. The health seeking behaviour of an individual is a product of a complex and dynamic interaction between several factors which either motivate or discourage an individual from seeking appropriate care. These factors can be dependent on individual's demographic characteristics, severity of illness, acceptable or persuasive societal norms, perceived health-provider attributes, and accessibility options of getting care^{1,2}.

Some studies have described models in order to explain the intricate processes that guide an individual to make decisions on how, when, where and from whom they want to access healthcare^{1,3,4}. The Health Belief Model (HBM) is the most common model and is often used to explain behavioural patterns relevant to healthcare. The Health Belief Model suggests that there are 6 major areas of individualised-perceptions required to determine a person's health seeking behaviour. These include the perceived severity; perceived susceptibility; perceived benefits; perceived barriers; cues to action, and self-efficacy⁴.

However, health practitioners and medical students in particular constitute a special group whose perceptions about their illnesses come from a standpoint of relative awareness of their conditions. They can easily assume the roles of an expert patient - by virtue of regular exposure to knowledge about various illnesses and how to go about their managements. With this in mind, we intend to determine in this study, the various health seeking behaviour of medical students in a tertiary institution, and how certain socio-demographic variables affect their health seeking behaviour.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Young people are exposed to a wide range of options when sick including seeking spiritual help, patronizing local pharmacies, self-medication and visit to a health facility. Medical students have the privilege of medical knowledge and can easily self-consult, self-diagnose and self-medicate⁵.

Studies have shown that medical doctors generally have a poor health seeking behaviour when they take ill and are therefore very poor at playing the role of a patient when necessary^{2,6,7}. Medical students who would invariably become doctors themselves may have been caught early in the web of inappropriate health seeking behaviour. A study among medical students in Goa, India showed that 66.3% of respondents had self-treated themselves while about 40% thought it was alright to self-investigate and self-treat themselves⁶.

The study at the University of Nigeria in Enugu State revealed medical students in Nigeria would rather visit a patent medicine store than visit a doctor when sick, they only seek help from a doctor when the symptoms are unbearable and when it affects their daily activities². These medical students graduate to become doctors and this attitude doesn't necessarily leave them. A Study in Nigeria has shown that most doctors would prefer informal consultations when they're sick as opposed to formal consultations, these informal consultations are sought from their close physician-friends. Only 35% of doctors consulted colleagues for treatment, two third of which were informal consultations⁸.

A study in Jos further observed the paucity of self-prescription for narcotics and psychotropic drugs among doctors, signifying that doctor may have preference for the spectrum of illnesses they are willing to admit they have or they may not be comfortable disclosing self-prescription of certain drugs. Whatever the case, this is in contrast to the several literatures that recognizes a high prevalence of depression and other psychological problems among doctors and other health professionals⁹.

According to the study done in Jos, Nigeria, 98.6% of medical doctors have self-prescribed at least once, 68.3% self-prescribed within the last 3 months of that study, and only 46.9% consulted a physician when they were ill⁹.

According to Fawibeet *al.*⁸, on medical care seeking behaviour of doctors in Kwara State, only 35% of those who had been ill in the last one year reportedly consulted another doctor. Still, over 61% of these consults were informal, sometimes occurring via phone calls, on the corridor, or

at home. We might easily feign that doctor engage in these sort of illness behaviors because of ignorance, however, a study by Adewoye *et al.* showed that the level of awareness about proper health seeking behaviour among doctors was very high, yet this did not translate into actual behavior whenever they fell ill¹⁰.

Even among medical directors who are top-most in the hierarchy of medical administration, self-prescription and self-treatment has been shown to be very common¹¹.

1.3 JUSTIFICATION

Although health seeking behaviour has been studied in several population groups who do not necessarily have knowledge about their health conditions, there is a need to assess the health seeking behaviour among a population group that understands the basic pathophysiology and therapeutic options of their disease condition. This will help to highlight possible reasons for a knowledge-action gap in seeking healthcare among those who are otherwise knowledgeable about their disease condition.

Young people have unique health challenges that require specialized care, different from the needs of adults and children. This includes psychosocial problems and problems arising from explorative behaviours e.g., alcohol abuse and unsafe sexual practices. However, one study revealed that in a university setting – a setting with an abundance of young people, medical students were observed to show the least patronage of the university’s health services among other students from the different faculties².

Also, several studies have reported on the prevalence of mental health problems and burnout among medical students globally, however, very few have highlighted their health seeking behaviour. We are aware of only one study in Nigeria done in 2016 which assessed the health seeking behaviour of students in the faculty of health science and technology in Enugu².

In this study, we hope to identify the various health seeking behaviours of medical students, find the relationship between various socio-demographic variables and the health seeking behaviour of medical students, and identify factors responsible for the various health seeking behaviour of medical students in the University of Uyo, Nigeria.

1.4 GENERAL OBJECTIVE

To determine the health seeking behaviour of medical students in the University of Uyo.

1.5 SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

To determine the various health seeking behaviour of medical students in the University of Uyo

To determine the relationship between socio-demographic variables and the health seeking behaviour of medical students in the University of Uyo

To identify and assess the prevailing factors that influence the health seeking behaviour of medical students in the university of Uyo

1.6 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

What are the various health seeking behaviours of medical students in the University of Uyo?

What are the effects of socio-demographic variables on the health seeking behaviour of medical students in the University of Uyo?

What are the factors that influence the health seeking behaviour of medical students in the University of Uyo?

1.7 HYPOTHESIS

Null Hypothesis

1. There is no relationship between the sociodemographic variables and the health seeking behaviour of medical students in the University of Uyo.
2. There is no relationship between the illness experience of medical students in the University of Uyo and their health seeking behaviour.

Alternate Hypothesis

1. There is a relationship between the sociodemographic variables and the health seeking behaviour of medical students in the University of Uyo.
2. There is a relationship between the illness experience of medical students in the University of Uyo and their health seeking behaviour.

CHAPTER 2 – LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

Healthcare seeking behaviour (HSB) has been defined as, "any action or inaction undertaken by individuals who perceive themselves to have a health problem or to be ill for the purpose of finding an appropriate remedy"¹. In the widest sense, health seeking behaviour and attitude includes all behaviours associated with establishing and maintaining a healthy physical, mental, social wellbeing (primary prevention) and also include behaviours that deal with any deviation from the normal state of health, by controlling risks (secondary prevention) and reducing the progression of an already established disease and rehabilitation (tertiary prevention)¹².

In particular, health-seeking behaviour can be described with data collected from information such as the time difference between the onset of an illness and getting in contact with a healthcare professional, type of healthcare provider patients sought help from, how compliant patient is with the recommended treatment, reasons for choice of healthcare professional and reasons for not seeking help from healthcare professionals¹².

Medical schools in Nigeria aim to train and produce competent and empathetic physicians to help the sick, advance medical knowledge, and promote public health¹ However, medical education is considered to be one of the most academically and emotionally demanding training programs of any profession¹³, and consequently, the time and emotional commitment necessary for medical students to devote to their training is extensive. Such demands and stress cause a negative effect on the students and can affect them physically, mentally and socially predisposing them to neglect their health or pay less attention to it.

Nigeria has over 36 medical schools with thousands of medical students nationwide undergoing trainings to become medical doctors and very little is known about their health seeking behaviour, as many of them self-diagnose and treat themselves when ill. This behaviour may continue when they become licensed doctors, the time which they may not want to accept patient roles and may seek appropriate care from their colleagues who are specialists in various fields. Medical students have different perception of symptoms and illness. Self-diagnosis and self-treatment are common behaviour among medical Students. By promoting appropriate healthseeking behaviour among medical students, it may have a ripple effect in promoting health seeking

behaviour among doctors and also among the general population. This is because medical students are future doctors, and doctors have the responsibility to guide the general populace on leading a healthy lifestyle.

2.2 MODELS OF HEALTH SEEKING BEHAVIOUR

Several factors (both external and intrinsic to an individual) have an influence on the overall response of individuals to their health and the use of available health care services. According to Tipping and Segall, these factors can be classified into two which include: factors that focus in the utilization of the system (health care seeking behaviour) and those factors that focus on the illness response (health seeking behaviour)¹⁴.

While Health care seeking behaviour focuses on the act or decision to patronize or engage health care channel or service, health seeking behaviour studies individuals' responses to ill health and investigates factors that make or prevent individuals from making healthy choices. Determinants of health care seeking behaviour could be economic, cultural, social or organizational and factors that influence these determinants include age, sex, cost of care, distance to facility, perceived quality etc¹⁴.

Health seeking behaviour on the other hand is interested in the behaviour of individuals when they fall ill and their subsequent response. Several models/theories of health seeking behaviour have been identified and include the health belief model, multidimensional health locus of control measure, protection motivation theory, theory of planned behaviour, social cognitive theory, self-determination theory, socio-ecological model, relapse prevention, theory of reasoned action, transtheoretical model or stages of change model, precaution adoption process model and diffusion of innovation model^{15,16}.

THE HEALTH BELIEF MODEL

Fig. 1 The "Health Belief Model" as predictor of preventive health behaviour

Rosenstock in 1966 and has become one of the most popular models of health behaviour. It was created to guide research on screening for tuberculosis. This model is a product of behavioural research and is an expectancy-value model^{15,16}. However, in health-related behaviour, the health belief model has been found to have a weak predictive power¹⁷.

According to this model, the probability that a person would take any health-related action depends on several factors that revolves around their perception about the consequences, severity of the condition; the benefits of acting, its cost and the risks of not acting. Components of the health belief model include:

- Perceived Susceptibility: this is an individual's perception of how much of a threat a particular condition is. This perception affects how the individual responds to that illness. The greater the estimate an individual makes of their vulnerability to a disease, the greater chances of acting to respond to the risk. However, this action is also affected by demographic variables, social pressure and personality¹⁸.
- Perceived Severity: This refers to the individual's estimation of the consequences or effects of being affected by a condition. The more serious an individual estimates condition should they come down with it, the more likely they are to take any action regarding the condition.

A combination of perceived susceptibility and perceived severity make up a threat¹⁹

- Perceived Benefits: This is based on a fundamental belief by an individual that a healthy behaviour or health protective action has the ability to be effective. For example, a person having sex with a partner whose health status is not known would only use a condom if they believe that it would be effective in protecting them against sexually transmitted infections.
- Perceived Barriers: Taking a health precautionary action or engaging in a health promoting behaviour may come with some costs or barriers. This could include financial costs, manpower, time, etc. The Health Belief Model posits that for individuals to engage in a health promoting action, they should be able to weigh the costs and the benefits and the benefits should outweigh the cost.

Combination of perceived effectiveness and perceived costs make up "the notion of outcome expectation"¹⁹.

- Cues to action: This refers to the triggers or prompts that engineer health-promotive action by individuals. An individual may be triggered by both intrinsic (like symptoms of a disease) or extrinsic factors (like the death of someone close to them from a condition they feel they are at risk of). For example, a person who has a high perceived severity of a disease may need just little trigger for them to undertake a health promotive behaviour while a person with low perceived susceptibility to a disease may need a bigger trigger for them to respond to similar disease condition.

- Self-efficacy: This refers to the confidence level of individuals in their ability to undertake a specific health promotive behaviour or action. This component of the health belief model was recently introduced in the 1970s¹⁷. Some mediating variables have an effect on the self-efficacy and include demographics, educational level, social and structural variables. These variables can also affect the perceived susceptibility and perceived severity of an illness and could have an overall effect on the health seeking behaviour.

A typical example of health seeking behaviour was described in a case report in Trupuri, India. This study can be used to illustrate the health belief model which seeks to explain the health seeking behaviour of individuals.

The study was carried out on a family of seven. The husband is illiterate but trained as a painter, wife is an undergraduate and three of the children are females while two are males. The first four births were carried out at home by traditional birth attendants; however, the last delivery was carried out in a healthcare institution (community health centre). Concerns were raised by the researchers as to why after four successful previous home deliveries, the wife would choose to patronize a health centre for the fifth delivery. The study revealed that the reasons for her behaviour were a constellation of several factors. First, she experienced pain during the fifth pregnancy and was scared of complications. This illustrates a perceived susceptibility and severity. Secondly, she was encouraged by financial incentive and prompt ambulance service by the government (perceived benefit) for those who patronized institutional deliveries. Also, she was better placed in decision making than her husband since she was better educated (mediating variable) however, she patronized traditional birth attendants for her first four deliveries as the family resided in a rural setting previously and had only moved to the urban region just before her fourth delivery. Having just moved to the urban region recently, she did not have enough time to make the decision to use institutional care for her fourth delivery. The media through advertorials and publicity of government's effort to improve maternal health care (cues to action) was also a determining factor which caused a change in her behaviour and subsequent use of institutional care for her fifth delivery²⁰.

Other models although not as common as the Health Belief Model, howbeit necessary to mention are listed below;

1. The Transtheoretical Model (Theory of Change): Captures change as a process rather than an event and was developed as a result of the innovators to engage with psychotherapy in the reduction of harm from tobacco smoking¹⁷. It has 6 stages.
2. The Social Cognitive Theory or Social Learning Theory: Developed in 1989 and believes in learning by observation from others (role models), imitation of their behaviours and positive reinforcements from external influences such as the media ²¹.

2.3 SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS AND HEALTH SEEKING BEHAVIOUR

Health seeking behavior can be traced to several sociodemographic characteristics of an individual, this includes age bracket, gender, marital status, level of education, course of study in school, level or class in school, even type of work.

According to a study²² done in a medical college in China, it was found that 14.8% of male students self-medicated while 16.2% of females self-medicated. It was also found out that 3.8% of male students self-medicated with anti-biotics while a total of 4.5% of females self-medicated with antibiotics. Also, 15.9% of people aged 16-20 years self-medicated, while 4.9% of 16-20 years used antibiotics. 15.6% of people aged 21-25 self-medicated while 3.7% of this population used antibiotics, 14.8% of people aged 26-40 self-medicated while 4.9% used antibiotics. It was also observed that 16.8% of people in study years 1-3 self-medicated while 19.5% of people in study years 4-8 self-medicated. For those who self-medicated with antibiotics, 2.5% of people in years 1-4 used antibiotics during self-medication while 3.4% in study years 4-8 used antibiotics during self-medication.

Another study done in Yemen²³ showed that among all medical students who self-medicated, 69.7% were males while 30.3% were females. It also showed that the class with the highest number of people that self-medicated was 4th year with 35.4%.

In Eastern Nepal, a study among medical students and dental students revealed that 51.1% of the total population used antibiotics that was self-prescribed²⁴. It also showed that students in year 5 had the highest percentage for self-prescribed antibiotics. Another study in a medical school in the same Nepal showed that 59.2% of all the males used drugs not prescribed by a doctor, while 61.1% of all female used drugs not prescribed by a doctor²⁵.

In the United States, a study²⁶ was carried out to determine the correlation of online health information seeking behavior among men compared to women, it showed that 49.17% of those who seek online health information were male, while 50.80% were females. 74.8% were married while 25.2% were unmarried, 53.3% lived in major cities while 46.7% do not live in major cities.

In Egypt, a study²⁷ was done among University students, 52.6% of all the males self-medicated while 65.8% of all the females self-medicated, 68.2% of those who lived in urban areas self-medicated while 57.5% of those who lived in rural areas self-medicated, 72.4% of medical students self-medicated while 52.6% of non-medical students self-medicated, 64.3% of married people self-medicated while 48.6% of unmarried people self-medicated, 61% of those in first grade self-medicated while 64.2% of those in final grade self-medicated.

Gender based health seeking behavior among adolescents in Soweto, South Africa also revealed more females who sought for medical care in the last 6 months compared to the males²⁸.

In Nigeria, a study carried out on Physicians in Jos University Teaching hospital showed that 45.2% of the male physician respondents consulted a physician when sick, while 55.2% of female physicians in the study consulted a physician when ill. Also, 45.7% of those below 40 years consulted a physician when ill while 55.6% of those above 40 years of age consulted a physician when ill. Also, 45.7% of those that have spent less than 10 years in practice consulted a physician when sick while 51.6% of those that have spent more than 10 years in practice consulted a doctor when ill⁹.

2.4 HEALTH SEEKING BEHAVIOUR AMONG HEALTH PROFESSIONALS

According to WHO, health professionals play a central and critical role in improving access and quality health care for the population. They provide essential services that promote health, prevent diseases and deliver health care services to individuals, families and communities based on the primary health care approach²⁹.

Health professionals are perceived to have good knowledge of ideal health seeking behaviors and they are expected to be aware of the regulations guiding self-care as spelt out in their adopted Code of Medical Ethics. The Nigerian Code of Medical Ethics for example states that " a doctor should avoid self-treatment and self-medication unless the illness is clearly minor or there is no

access to a colleague³⁰. However, research shows that Nigerian doctors have a poor knowledge of medical ethics³¹. Furthermore, few studies have posited that health seeking behaviour is better when people have good knowledge on the nature of the illness³², however this is in contrast with observable health seeking behaviour among doctors.

The reason for imploring doctors to avoid self-care stems from the threat posed by excessive emotional interest to sound clinical judgement. However, several papers attest to the fact that doctors have a poor health seeking behaviour, often identified by self-diagnosis, self-prescription, self-treatment, and underestimation or overestimation of severity of illness^{8,33,34}.

According to a study done in the university of Macedonia on self-medication, 94% of doctors agreed they could self-treat acute minor illnesses, 37% agreed they could self-treat chronic conditions and 42% agreed that they could order their own blood test for diagnostic purposes³⁵.

One study in western Nigeria on the awareness of proper health seeking behaviors among doctors and nurses showed that awareness about acceptable health seeking behaviour was high but however did not translate to appropriate illness behaviour¹⁰. There was apathy for regular check-up and self-medication was high among this group of health workers. The paper further mentioned that decreasing age and year of experience, increasing working hours, lack of health insurance, fear of confidentiality and lack of satisfaction with health services greatly increased the likelihood of self-medication.

Doctors often find it difficult to fit into the patient role for several reasons. Some of these include time pressure, level of stigmatization associated with the illness, unwillingness to portray weakness to patients and other colleagues, and a lack of knowledge³⁶.

2.5 OTHER FACTORS INFLUENCING THE HEALTH SEEKING BEHAVIOUR OF MEDICAL STUDENTS

Apart from the effect of sociodemographic factors on the health seeking behaviour of medical students, there might be some other inconspicuous factors which are peculiar to medical students and precipitated by the discomfort of seeking proper medical care in the same setting as where their learning takes place. For instance, a pilot study on the healthcare needs, practices and concerns of medical students revealed that they had concerns about confidentiality and experiencing

a dual role as both student and patient at their training institution, while also believing that revealing their status on certain medical conditions might bring their training to a halt³⁷.

Quite unsurprisingly, the feeling of overconfidence about their knowledge of disease pathology and prognostication often leads to medical students making poor health decisions. According to a paper in the University of Sharjah, it was observed that medical students self-evaluated and also self-prescribed mainly because they assumed they had enough knowledge to do so, further claiming they understood the signs and symptoms of the disease to decide whether they needed medical attention or not⁷. Closely associated with overconfidence is negligence. Another paper done in a teaching hospital in Nepal noted that the most common factor leading to self-medication among medical students was due to downplaying of symptoms as being minor⁵, often times, they are likely to visit the health facility when their assumed minor symptoms become life threatening.

Concerning self-diagnosis and self-medication, Clare Hooper et al. suggested that medical students assume early on that it is appropriate for doctors to self-investigate, self-refer and self-medicate³⁸. The study was done in a medical school in London, where it is difficult for medical students to self-prescribe probably due to stringent regulation on drug purchase in the UK, however in Nigeria, medical students are well known to self-prescribe especially with increasing level of clinical knowledge^{39,40}.

From a spiritual standpoint, many health professionals strongly recognize the importance of spirituality in healthcare. For example, Christina Puchalski noted that spirituality helped patients cope with terminal illness and enhanced recovery, while doctors could better counsel and understand patient's need if they discussed spirituality openly and in a nonjudgmental manner⁴¹.

Also, Cheryl et al⁴² noted that spirituality helps people to live a healthy life by moderating certain harmful health behaviour such as alcoholism, smoking and harmful sexual practices, however, they also noted that spirituality could be harmful to patients especially when it perceives illness as a reward for sin. Perhaps where spirituality negatively affects HSB of medical students is the tendency to seek spiritual help before giving orthodox care a chance. Ajaegbu and Ubochi² noted that 10% of respondents in their study on the HSB among undergraduates in the faculty of health science reacted to their symptoms by using spiritual tools with a few of them believing that it is against their belief to seek nonreligious help.

Due to technological advancements, the health sector has experienced unprecedented knowledge explosion to the extent that anyone with a mobile phone could self-diagnose and self-treat despite lacking a basic understanding of the medical science behind managing diseases. Roberto et al⁴³ referred to the use of internet for the self-treatment of Sexually Transmitted Infections as a health hazard, while stating that those who do so lack information on adverse effects, drug interactions and contraindications.

However, what happens if those who use the internet for self-treatment have a relatively good understanding of the medical science behind the management of their condition? Such as in the case of medical students. Several studies^{2,6,7,44} have attested to the use of internet information for self-treatment by medical students. Perhaps this information is further supplemented by their medical textbooks where detail description of case managements may be found.

CHAPTER 3 – METHODOLOGY

3.1 STUDY AREA

Akwa Ibom State is located in the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria. It is situated in the Niger Delta region and lies between latitude $4^{\circ}32'N$ and $5^{\circ}33'N$, and Longitude $7^{\circ}25'E$ and $8^{\circ}25'E$. It is one of the oil and gas producing states in Nigeria significantly impacting on the high cost of living of its citizens. The State has an estimated population of 5.5 million and Uyo, its capital has an estimated population of 430,000^{45,46}. The state has predominantly two religions which are Christianity and Traditional^{47,48}.

Akwa Ibom State is an almost unitary cultural state where ethics, morals, taboos, customs and traditions are the same throughout the State. These cultural similarities bind the people together especially in such areas as dressing, dances, songs, rituals, folklores, myths and beliefs. These similarities also promote the use of folk remedies, because it fits into their beliefs and is culturally acceptable. Apart from this, Over-the-counter medications are widely available in pharmaceutical stores and chemist shops within the city, many times manned by uncertified personnel and favoring self-medication and wrong prescription for commonly known symptoms⁴⁹.

This study was carried out in the University of Uyo, also called “Uniuyo”, a tertiary institution located in Uyo, the capital of Akwa Ibom State. It was established in 1991. It was formerly University of Cross River States (UniCross) which was established in 1987⁵⁰.

The University operates from four campuses namely: The Permanent site or Main Campus located at Nwaniba Road, the Town Campus located at Ikpa Road, The Annex campus also located at Ikpa Road, and the Ime Umanah Campus, Ediene-Abak. The University of Uyo Teaching Hospital is sometimes classified as one of the campuses. The University has twelve faculties excluding the School of Continuing Education. The University has a population of over 30,000 students⁵¹.

Faculty of Clinical Sciences is one of the 4 main faculties in the College of Health Sciences, the others include, Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences; Faculty of Allied Health Sciences; and the Faculty of Dentistry. The Faculty of Clinical Sciences does not directly admit students but receives students already admitted by the College of Health Sciences to study Medicine and Surgery from their 3rd year of medical training. The faculty receives students from the Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences after they have successfully completed their Basic Medical Science courses in Anatomy,

Biochemistry and Physiology (Part 1 MB, BS popularly called second MB. The Faculty of Clinical Science has about 600 students. These group of students have their lectures in the Annex Campus and the ETF Block in the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital located along Abak road, Uyo³⁸.

3.2 STUDY DESIGN & POPULATION

The study was an institution-based cross-sectional study. The study population included all students admitted by the College of Health Sciences to study Medicine and Surgery, and who met inclusion criteria.

3.3 SELECTION CRITERIA

Inclusion Criteria

1. Medical Students of the University of Uyo currently in their 1st to 6th year of medical training.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Listed authors from this study.
2. Medical students who recently concluded their Part IV MB exams
3. Medical students chronically absent from school due to suspension of studies or illness.
4. Medical students who did not give consent to be included in the study.

3.4 SAMPLE SIZE DETERMINATION

Sample size was determined using the Fisher's formula:

$$N = (Z^2 pq) / d^2$$

and using the formula for a population size less than 10,000

$$N_f = n / (1 + n/N), \text{ Where;}$$

N = minimum sample size, Z = 1.96, level of significance

$p = 0.5$ assumed prevalence of poor health seeking behaviour among doctors and nurses in Federal Teaching Hospital Ido-Ekiti ¹⁰

$q = 1 - p = 0.5$, $d =$ margin of error

Margin of error (degree of precision) = 0.05

$N_f =$ Corrected sample size for a population size less than 10,000

$$n = (1.96^2 * 0.5 * 0.5) / 0.05^2 = 384$$

For a population size of 628,

$$N_f = 628 / (1 + (628 / 384)) = 238$$

An upward adjustment of 10 percent was added to correct for nonresponse and discrepant entries bringing total sample size to 262.

3.5 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

The number of students selected from each level was determined by proportionate allocation as presented below;

Level	Population Size (n)	Allocation ($s = (n/N) * 262$)
100	43	18
200	99	41
300	103	43
400	129	54
500 B*	109	46
500 A*	87	36
600	58	24
Total(N)	628	262

Table 3.1 showing the allocation of participants per class level. * The 500-level class had both a senior arm(A) and a junior arm(B).

A simple random sampling method was used to select the allocated number of respondents from each level. A copy of the class register was requested from the class representatives and was used as a sampling frame. The interval of selection was estimated as the fraction of total eligible

participants in each class to the allocated participants for that class. With the permission of the class representatives of each class, study participants were approached in their respective classes and at the hostel of residence using the class list as a table of random numbers. The hostel is occupied by both male and female medical students. In each class, questionnaires were shared by the research assistants to every third eligible respondent that was approached.

3.6 DATA COLLECTION

An anonymous semi-structured self-administered questionnaire was developed. The questionnaire was adapted from a previous study² and contained the following sections;

- A. Socio-demographic data of respondents including age, sex, marital status, religion and current level of study.
- B. Illness experience in the last 6 months
- C. Illness response in the last 6 months
- D. Factors affecting choice of illness behaviour

The questionnaire was shared pro forma to 26 Pharmacy students for the purpose of pretesting and validation before putting it to use. We chose Pharmacy students for the pre-test because of a comparative exposure to health-related training on the therapeutic use of drugs. No financial or any other type of reward was given to respondents. Class representatives from each class served as research assistants for this study. Research assistants were initially trained on how to administer and collect the questionnaire and are acknowledged at the end of the study.

3.7 DATA MANAGEMENT/ANALYSIS

Questionnaires were compiled and stored in a cabinet kept for this purpose. Data was then cleansed and inputted into Microsoft Office Excel 2016. Next, data was extracted from Microsoft Excel and descriptively analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences SPSS (Version 26). Results were presented in frequencies and percentages and graphically represented using bar charts and pie charts. Quantitative variables were summarised as means and standard deviations. Pearson and Chi-squared test were used to compare 2 variables and level of significance was set at 5%.

3.8 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

Ethical approval was sought from the Ethical Review Committee of the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital. A written informed consent was obtained from each willing participant. The written informed consent contained,

1. **PURPOSE OF THE STUDY:** The purpose of the study was to determine the Health Seeking Behaviour of Medical Students of the University of Uyo. This was explained to participants.
2. **PROCEDURE OF THE RESEARCH:** Participants were expected to fill a questionnaire regarding their health seeking behaviour and factors that influence them.
3. **RISK:** The study was not invasive and participants were only made to fill a questionnaire. There were no other risks from participating in this study.
4. **COST:** Participation in this study cost participants only a few minutes of their time.
5. **BENEFITS:** Information gotten from this study would add to the body of knowledge and help healthcare workers understand the factors influencing the health seeking behaviour of medical students with a view to improve their health.
6. **CONFIDENTIALITY:** All information obtained in this study was not linked to participants in any way. Names or any other method of identification were not used in any publications or reports from this study.
7. **VOLUNTARINESS:** Participation in this research was entirely voluntary. Participants had the right to opt out or decline from responding.
8. **CONSEQUENCES OF WITHDRAWAL:** There were no consequences for people who chose not to participate in this study.

A copy of the written informed consent as well as the questionnaire is attached to the proposal as appendix.

3.9 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The timeline of the study coincides with the preparation for our final exams. Thus, we recruited class representatives from each class as research assistants to aid this study.

Financial limitations as researchers were fulltime students. We sourced for funds externally to fund this project.

There is no other medical school in Akwa Ibom state and pre-test was carried out among pharmacy students

The result is based on perception of respondents and may not be the true reflection of their health seeking behaviour. Thus, we hope that ensuring confidentiality will help overcome this problem.

CHAPTER 4 – RESULTS

4.1 SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

Table 1. Sociodemographic characteristics of participants (N = 262)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sex		
Male	155	59.2
Female	107	40.8
Age		
<25 years	216	82.4
≥25 years	46	17.6
Level		
100L [‡]	19	7.3
200L [‡]	41	15.6
300L [‡]	43	16.4
400L [§]	54	20.6
500LB [§]	46	17.6
500LA [§]	36	13.7
600L [§]	23	8.8
Marital Status		
Single	262	100.0
Married	0	0.0
Religion		
Christian	255	97.3
Traditional	7	2.7
Denomination		
Pentecostal	156	61.2
Orthodox	52	20.4
Others	47	18.4

[‡]Preclinical levels [§]Clinical levels

From Table 1. A total of two hundred and sixty-two respondents (262) participated in the study. One hundred and fifty-five (59.2%) of all respondents were males. The majority (216, 82.4%) were less than 25 years of age. The mean age by sex was 22.7 (± 3.11) for males and 21.6 (± 2.52) for

females. One hundred and three (39.3%) respondents were from the preclinical levels (100L to 300L) while 159 (60.7%) respondents were from the clinical levels (400L to 600L). All respondents were single and the majority (255, 97.3%) were Christians.

4.2 ILLNESS EXPERIENCE OF RESPONDENTS

Table 2. Illness experience of respondents in the last 6 months

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Experienced illness symptoms in the last 6 months		
No	20	7.6
Yes	242	92.4
Symptoms experienced in the last 6 months		
Headache	181	69.1
Fever	174	66.4
Low Mood/Depression	119	45.4
Catarrh	97	37.0
Cough	93	35.5
General Body Weakness	74	28.2
Sore throat	66	25.2
Abdominal pain	62	23.7
Joint pain	39	14.9
Chest pain	33	12.6
Waist pain	29	11.1
Eye problems	29	11.1
Breathlessness	18	6.9
Dental problems	15	5.7
Penile/vaginal discharge	13	5.0
Boil	12	4.6
Injury	1	0.4
Malaise	1	0.4
Mouth Ulcers	1	0.4
Seizure	1	0.4
Diarrhea	1	0.4

Table 2. The majority (242, 92.4%) had experienced at least one illness symptom in the last 6 months. Of those who had experienced illness symptoms in the last 6 months, the top ten (10) symptoms were headache (181, 69.1%), fever (174, 66.4%), low mood or depressive state (119, 45.4%), catarrh (97, 37.0%), cough (93, 35.5%), general body weakness (74, 28.2%), sore throat (66, 25.2%), abdominal pain (62, 23.7%), joint pain (39, 14.9%), and chest pain (33, 12.6%).

4.3 ILLNESS RESPONSE OF RESPONDENTS

Table 3. Illness response in the last 6 months

Variable	Freq	Percentage (%)
Usual response to illness experience (n=246)		
Went to the pharmacy/chemist	125	50.8
Rest and did nothing	58	23.6
Consulted a colleague	24	9.8
Visited the hospital at once	21	8.5
Browsed the internet	8	3.3
Used spiritual tools	6	2.4
Took herbal medication/concoction	4	1.6
Eventually visited the hospital (n=244)		
No	180	73.8
Yes	64	26.2
Reason for eventually visiting the hospital (n=64)		
Immediately symptoms appeared	24	37.5
Discomfort/pain was unbearable	21	32.8
Persuaded by family/friends	9	14.1
Someone with similar illness died	4	6.3
Random visits even without symptoms	3	4.7
Affected ability to cope academically	3	4.7

From Table 3. The commonest response to illness experience was going to the pharmacy (125, 50.8%), followed by resting and doing nothing (58, 23.6%). Twenty-four (9.8%) respondents had consulted a colleague, 8 (3.3%) respondents browsed the internet for their symptoms, 6 (2.4%) respondents used spiritual tools such as praying and fasting, while 4 (1.6%) respondents took herbal medications. Only 21 (8.5%) of those who had experienced illness symptoms visited the hospital at once.

Sixty-four (26.2%) of all those who had at least one illness response eventually visited the hospital. Twenty-four (37.5%) respondents said they visited the hospital immediately symptoms appeared, 21(32.8%) said they eventually visited the hospital when the discomfort and pain from their illness was unbearable. Nine (14.1%) of those who eventually visited the hospital were persuaded by either family members or friends. Four (6.3%) respondents eventually visited the hospital because someone they knew had died from similar illness symptoms. Three (4.7%) decided to visit the hospital because their academics had been negatively impacted.

4.4 ASSOCIATION BETWEEN SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES AND ILLNESS RESPONSE OF RESPONDENTS

Table 4.1: Association between sociodemographic variables and illness response of respondents

Illness response	Gender		χ^2 , p	Age		p
	Male	Female		<25 years (%)	≥25 years(%)	
	144	102		202	44	
Rest and did nothing						
No	113(78.5)	75(73.5)	0.81	151(74.8)	37(84.1)	1.75
Yes	31(21.5)	27(26.5)	0.368	51(25.2)	7(15.9)	0.186
Took herbal medication						
No	144(100)	98(96.1)	0.029 [‡]	200(99.0)	42(95.5)	0.148 [‡]
Yes	0 (0)	4(3.9)		2(1.0)	2(4.5)	
Went to pharmacy/chemist						
No	60(41.7)	61(59.8)	7.86	100(49.5)	21(47.7)	0.05
Yes	84(58.3)	41(40.2)	0.005	102(50.5)	23(52.3)	0.831
Browsed the internet						
No	141(97.9)	97(95.1)	0.282 [‡]	195(96.5)	43(97.7)	1.000 [‡]
Yes	3(2.1)	5(4.9)		7(3.5)	1(2.3)	
Consulted a colleague						
No	135(93.8)	87(85.3)	4.85	182(90.1)	40(90.9)	1.000 [‡]
Yes	9(6.3)	15(14.7)	0.028	20(9.9)	4(9.1)	
Used spiritual tools						
No	141(97.9)	99(97.1)	0.694 [‡]	198(98.0)	42(95.5)	0.292 [‡]
Yes	3(2.1)	3(2.9)		4(2.0)	2(4.5)	
Visited hospital at once						
No	130(90.3)	95(93.1)	0.63	186(92.1)	39(88.6)	0.549 [‡]
Yes	14(9.7)	7(6.9)	0.429	16(7.9)	5(8.5)	

[‡] Fisher's exact test, p = p value

Table 4.1. Gender was significantly associated with taking herbal medication ($p = .029$), going to the pharmacy ($\chi^2=7.86$, $df=1$, $p = .005$), and consulting a colleague ($\chi^2=4.85$, $df=1$, $p = .028$). Age was not associated with any of the illness responses. More females (3.9%) took herbal medication compared to males (0.0%). More males went to the pharmacy (58.3%) compared to females (40.2%). Also, more females consulted a colleague (14.7%) compared to males(6.3%).

Table 4.2: Association between sociodemographic variables and illness response of respondents

Illness response	Clinical Level		χ^2 , p	Religion		p
	PC	C		Christian	Traditional	
	94	152		239	7	
Rest and did nothing						
No	76(80.9)	112(73.7)	1.66,	182(76.2)	6(85.7)	1.000 ‡
Yes	18(19.1)	40(26.3)	0.198	57(23.8)	1(14.3)	
Took herbal medication						
No	92(97.9)	150(98.7)	0.638 ‡	235(98.3)	7(100)	1.000 ‡
Yes	2(2.1)	2(1.3)		4(1.7)	0(0.0)	
Went to pharmacy/chemist						
No	38(40.4)	83(54.6)	4.67,	119(49.8)	2(28.6)	0.447 ‡
Yes	56(59.6)	69(45.4)	0.031	120(50.2)	5(71.4)	
Browsed the internet						
No	91(96.8)	147(96.7)	1.000 ‡	231(96.7)	7(100)	1.000 ‡
Yes	3(3.2)	5(3.3)		8(3.3)	0(0.0)	
Consulted a colleague						
No	89(94.7)	133(87.5)	3.40	215(90.0)	7(100)	1.000 ‡
Yes	5(5.3)	19(12.5)	0.065	24(10.0)	0(0.0)	
Used spiritual tools						
No	92(97.9)	148(97.4)	1.000‡	234(97.9)	6(85.7)	0.161 ‡
Yes	2(2.1)	4(2.6)		5(2.1)	1(14.3)	
Visited hospital at once						
No	86(91.5)	139(91.4)	0.00	218(91.2)	7(100)	1.000 ‡
Yes	8(8.5)	13(8.6)	0.991	21(8.8)	0(0.0)	

‡ Fisher's exact test, p = p value, PC = preclinical, C = clinical

Table 4.2. Level of training was significantly associated with going to the pharmacy ($\chi^2=4.67$, $df=1$, $p = .031$). A higher proportion of preclinical students (59.6%) went to the pharmacy compared to the clinical student(45.4%). Religion, however, was not significantly associated with any illness response.

4.5 FACTORS AFFECTING CHOICE OF ILLNESS BEHAVIOUR

Table 5. Reasons for choice of illness behaviour

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Rest and did nothing(n=58)		
Minor illness	58	100.0
Previous experience which resolved on its own	27	46.6
Took herbal medication(n=4)		
Saves time	4	100.0
Cultural disposition	3	75.0
More effective than orthodox care	3	75.0
Cheaper	2	50.0
Went to the pharmacy/chemist (n=125)		
Easily accessible	74	59.2
Cheaper	16	12.8
Worked for a friend	13	10.4
Worked for me previously	2	1.6
Just felt like going	1	0.8
Browsed the internet (n=8)		
Easily accessible	7	87.5
Confidential	6	75.0
Cheaper	2	25.0
Saves time	2	25.0
Worked for me previously	2	25.0
Consulted a colleague (n=24)		
Colleague is more experienced	13	54.2
Easily accessible	12	50.0
Trusts colleague	5	20.8
Cheaper	2	8.3
Saves times	2	8.3
Used spiritual tools (n=6)		
Accessible	3	50.0
Effective	3	50.0
Reflex	1	16.7
Cheaper	1	16.7
Visited hospital at once(n=21)		
Effective	14	66.7
Competence of health workers	9	42.9
Symptoms are major	8	14.3
Easily accessible	3	38.1
Cheaper	3	14.3
Time saving	2	9.5

With respect to the reasons for the choice of illness behaviour, of the 58 respondents who rested and did nothing, all 58 (100.0%) did so because their illness symptoms were perceived to be minor, 27 (46.6%) also rested and did nothing because they had had similar experience in the past which resolved on its own without any intervention. Of the 4 respondents who took herbal medication, 1 (75.0%) did so because of their cultural disposition, 4(100%) did so because it saved their time, 3(75.0%) did so before they considered it more effective than orthodox care, while 2 (50.0%) did so because they considered it cheaper.

Of the 125 respondents who had visited the pharmacy, 74 (59.2%) did so because they considered it to be easily accessible, 16 (12.8%) found it cheaper, 13 (10.4%) did so because it had worked for a friend previously, 2 (1.6%) did so because it had worked for them previously, and only 1 (0.8%) respondent visited the pharmacy because they just felt like going.

Among those who had browsed the internet for their illness symptoms, 7(87.5%) did so because they found it easily accessible, 6(75.0%) did so because they found it confidential, 2(25.0%) of these respondents each found it cheaper, time saving and previously effective.

Of the 24 respondents who had consulted their colleague concerning their illness symptoms, 13(54.2%) said they did so because their colleague was considered more experienced, 12(50.0%) did so because their colleagues were easily accessible, 5(20.8%) did so because they trusted their colleagues, 2(8.3%) respondents each consulted their colleagues because they considered it cheaper and time saving.

3(50.0%) of those who used spiritual tools did so because they considered it effective and accessible. 1(16.7%) respondent said it was cheaper, while another 1(16.7%) respondent said they resorted to using spiritual tools because it was a reflex response.

Of the 21 respondents who had visited the hospitals at once, 14(66.7%) did so because it was effective, 9 (42.9%) did so because of the competence of the health workers, 8(38.1%) did so because they considered their illness to be major, 3 (14.3%) respondents each said it was cheaper and easily accessible, only 2(9.5%) respondents in this category said it was time saving.

Table 6. Factors associated with resting and doing nothing(N = 246)

Variable	Rest and did nothing		χ^2 , p value
	No n=188	Yes n=58	
Minor illness			
No	167(88.8)	21(11.2)	68.12,
Yes	21(36.2)	37(63.8)	<0.001*
Previous experience which resolved on its own			
No	179(81.7)	40(18.3)	31.25,
Yes	9(33.3)	18(66.7)	<0.001*

* p < 0.05

Table 6. Perceiving illness experience as minor was significantly associated with resting and doing nothing ($\chi^2=68.12$, df=1, p <0.001). Likewise, having a previous experience of similar illness which resolved without any intervention was significantly associated with resting and doing nothing ($\chi^2=31.25$, df=1, p = <0.001).

Table 7. Factors associated with taking herbal medications (N = 246)

Variable	Took herbal medication		χ^2 , p value
	No n=242	Yes n=4	
Cultural disposition			
No	239(98.4)	4(1.6)	1.000 †
Yes	3(100)	0 (0.0)	
Saves time			
No	238(98.3)	4(1.7)	1.000 †
Yes	4(100)	0 (0.0)	
More effective than orthodox care			
No	241(99.2)	2(0.8)	0.001†
Yes	1(33.3)	2(66.7)	
Cheaper			
No	240(98.4)	4(1.6)	1.000 †
Yes	2(100)	0(0.0)	

† Fisher's exact test

Table 7. perceiving herbal medications/concoctions to be more effective than orthodox care was significantly associated with taking herbal medication (p = 0.001, Fisher's exact).

Table 8. Factors associated with going to the pharmacy (N = 246).

Variable	Went to pharmacy		χ^2 , p value
	No n= 121	Yes n=125	
Easily accessible			
No	114(66.3)	58(33.7)	66.83, <0.001*
Yes	7(9.5)	67(90.5)	
Worked for a friend			
No	120(51.5)	113(48.5)	9.46, 0.002*
Yes	1(7.7)	12(92.3)	
Cheaper			
No	119(51.7)	111(48.3)	9.22, 0.002*
Yes	2(12.5)	14(87.5)	

* p <0.05

Table 8. ease of access ($\chi^2=66.83$, df=1, p< .001), positive outcome from a friend who had similar experience($\chi^2=9.46$, df=1, p = .002), and a perception of being cheap ($\chi^2=9.22$, df=1, p = .002), were all significantly associated with going to the pharmacy.

Table 9. Factors associated with browsing the internet (N = 246).

Variable	Browsed the internet		p value
	No n=238	Yes n=8	
Easily accessible			
No	233(97.5)	6(2.5)	0.018[†]
Yes	5(71.4)	2(28.6)	
Cheaper			
No	237(97.1)	7(2.9)	0.064 [†]
Yes	1(50.0)	1(50.0)	
Saves time			
No	237(97.1)	7(2.9)	0.064 [†]
Yes	1(50.0)	1(50.0)	
Confidential			
No	234(97.5)	6(2.5)	0.013 [†]
Yes	4(66.7)	2(33.3)	
Worked for me previously			
No	237(97.1)	7(2.9)	0.064 [†]
Yes	1(50.0)	1(50.0)	

[†] Fisher's exact test

Table 9. easy accessibility($p = .018$) and perceived confidentiality($p = .013$) were significantly associated with browsing the internet.

Table 10. Factors associated with consulting a colleague (N = 246).

Variable	Consulted colleague		p value
	No n=222	Yes n=24	
Easily accessible			
No	222(94.9)	12(5.1)	<0.001 [†]
Yes	0 (0.0)	12(100)	
Cheaper			
No	222(91.0)	22(9.0)	0.009 [†]
Yes	0 (0.0)	2(100)	
Trusts colleague			
No	221(91.7)	20(8.3)	<0.001 [†]
Yes	1(20.0)	4(80.0)	
Colleague is more experienced			
No	221(94.8)	12(5.2)	<0.001 [†]
Yes	1(7.7)	12(92.3)	

[†] Fisher's exact test

Table 10. easy accessibility ($p < .001$), being cheaper($p = .009$), trust in the clinical judgement of a colleague ($p < .001$), and perceived experience of colleague ($p < .001$) were all significantly associated with consulting a colleague as illness response.

Table 11. Factors associated with using spiritual tools (N = 246).

Variable	Used spiritual tools		p value
	No n=240	Yes n=6	
Cheaper			
No	240(98.0)	5(2.0)	0.024 [†]
Yes	0 (0.0)	1(100)	
Easily accessible			
No	238(97.9)	5(2.1)	.072 [†]
Yes	2(66.7)	1(33.3)	
Effective			
No	238(97.9)	5(2.1)	.072 [†]
Yes	2(66.7)	1(33.3)	

[†] Fisher's exact test

Table 11. Only the perception of being cheap ($p = .024$) was significantly associated with using spiritual tools as an illness response.

Table 12. Factors associated with visiting the hospital at once ($N = 246$).

Variable	Visited hospital		p value
	No n=225	Yes n=21	
Easily accessible			
No	224(92.2)	19(7.8)	0.020 [†]
Yes	1(33.3)	2(66.7)	
More effective			
No	221(95.3)	11(4.7)	<0.001 [†]
Yes	4 (28.6)	10(71.4)	
Major symptoms			
No	222(93.3)	16(6.7)	<0.001 [†]
Yes	3(37.5)	5(62.5)	
Cheaper			
No	224(92.2)	19(7.8)	0.020 [†]
Yes	1(33.3)	2(66.7)	
Competence of health workers			
No	220(92.8)	17(7.2)	0.004 [†]
Yes	5(55.6)	4(44.4)	

[†] Fisher's exact test

Table 12. being more effective and perceiving illness symptoms as major were both significantly associated with visiting the hospital at once ($p < .001$). Likewise, easy accessibility and a perception of being cheap were significantly associated with visiting the hospital at once ($p = .020$). Also, the believe that health workers in the hospital were competent was significantly associated with visiting the hospital at once ($p = .004$).

CHAPTER 5 – DISCUSSION

Following the analysis of the data collected from our sample of medical students in the University of Uyo, 92.4% of respondents experienced at least one illness symptom. This was quite similar to the finding by Ajaegbu et al² where 98.7% had experienced at least one illness symptom. However, Vaz et al.⁶ and Mukta et al.⁵ found lower proportion of respondents (80.4% and 67% respectively) who had had at least one illness symptom. This might be explained by the possible effect of recall bias in their studies where respondents were asked to recall their illness symptoms in the past 12 months.

The top five commonest symptoms in our study were headache(69.1%), fever(66.4%), low mood/depression(45.4%), catarrh(37.0%) and cough(35.5%). In a similar study carried out among healthcare students in Enugu, Nigeria², out of the respondents who reported symptoms of illness, 83.9% experienced headache, 97.3% percent had fever and 97.3% percent had cough and catarrh. While the commonest symptoms from our study also included fever and headache, low mood was reported to be the third commonest symptom and was experienced by 45.4% of respondents. This could be explained by the psychological trauma on respondents due to the prolonged industrial action by the Academic Staff Union of Universities coupled with the intense demands associated with medical training.

While psychiatric symptoms were not captured in other studies and thus cannot be compared, our study exposes a neglected area of health concern among medical students which affects a significant proportion of medical students and provides an interesting area of further research to explore the reasons for this incidence.

The top twocommonest health seeking behaviour among medical students in the University of Uyo were visiting the pharmacy 125(50.8%) and doing nothing 58(23.6%). Only 21 (8.5%) respondents visited the health facility at once. This is similar to the finding by Ajaegbu et al² where the top two commonest illness responses were going to a patent medicine dealer 83(27.9%) and doing nothing 72(24.1%). However, the study found a much higher proportion of respondents who visited the hospital at once (22.8%) compared to our study (8.5%), and a lower proportion of respondents who visited the pharmacy (27.9%) compared to our study (50.8%). The possible explanation for this difference could be because the other study included other departments (Nursing, Medical Lab Science, Radiography) who may not have similar level of training on the pharmacological management of common illnesses, and may decide to play safe by visiting the

health facility first. This further exposes the poor illness response prevalent within our study population.

More male respondents 84 (58.3%) visited the pharmacy first rather than visiting the hospital at once compared to females 41 (40.2%) and gender was significantly associated with going to the pharmacy ($\chi^2=7.86$, $df=1$, $p = .005$). This was similar to the study by Kanwal et al.²³ where more males than females procured medicine without initial medical approval. Furthermore, this study found that more preclinical students visited the pharmacy at once (59.6%) compared to clinical students (45.4%), also, clinical level was significantly associated with visiting the pharmacy at once ($\chi^2=4.67$, $df=1$, $p = .031$). This could be explained by a better knowledge of the dangers of self-medication and antimicrobial resistance amongst clinical students.

More female respondents (14.7%) consulted a colleague compared to male respondents. Pearson's chi-squared test revealed that gender was significantly associated with consulting a colleague. The reason for more females consulting a colleague could be due to their need for a second thought on specific female-related health problems which required confidentiality and experience from a colleague with similar problem. Although more male respondents visited the hospital at once 14 (9.7%) versus 7 (6.9%) for females, gender was not significantly associated with visiting the hospital at once.

The commonest reasons for resting and doing nothing was a perception of illness symptoms as minor 58 (100%) followed by having previous illness experience which resolved without intervention 27 (46.6%). Both reasons were significantly associated with resting and doing nothing, ($\chi^2=68.12$, $df=1$, $p < 0.001$) and ($\chi^2=31.25$, $df=1$, $p < 0.001$) respectively. This could be because medical students may consider themselves better able to identify minor symptoms, and those who have had previous experience which resolved spontaneously might take this as a cue for inaction.

It was interesting to find that 2 of the 4 medical students whose usual response was taking herbal medication, found this illness response more effective than orthodox care ($p = 0.001$, Fisher's exact). This could mean that good clinical knowledge might not necessarily discourage the use of complementary and alternative medicine (CAM).

The commonest reason for visiting the pharmacy was easy accessibility (59.2%), this was in contrast to the study by Ajaegbu et al.² where most respondents (25.3%) visited the pharmacy because they found it time saving. Ease of access ($p < 0.001$), positive outcome from a friend who had similar previous experience ($p = 0.002$), and being cheaper ($p = 0.002$) were all associated with going to the pharmacy. Medical students could be more motivated to get drugs from the pharmacy

especially in a setting where over-the-counter (OTC) medications are relatively cheap and with little or no access restriction.

Ease of access ($p<0.001$), being cheaper ($p=0.009$), trust in colleague ($p<0.001$), and considering a colleague to be more experienced ($p<0.001$) were significantly associated with consulting a colleague. This could be because informal discussions with more experienced colleagues could take place in the hostel of residence, thereby boycotting hospital bureaucracy, cost of care and transport logistics. Furthermore, said colleagues could be practising young physicians/house officers who might be considered more experienced and approachable.

In this study, 14 (66.7%) of those who visited the hospital at once, did so because they found it effective, while 9 (42.9%) did so because of the competence of health professionals. This was partially in contrast to Ajaegbu et al.² where most respondents who visited the hospital, did so because they believed their symptoms were major (33.8%) followed by the perception that it was more effective (29.4%). Being more effective ($p<0.001$) and perception of illness symptoms as being major ($p<0.001$) were significantly associated with visiting the hospital at once. This could be because medical students may consider themselves better able to identify red flag symptoms, which could negatively impact their academic. Such illness symptoms may require expert management from the hospital.

5.1 CONCLUSION

Medical students in the University of Uyo have a poor health seeking behaviour characterised mostly by visiting the pharmacy to purchase drugs and doing nothing until symptoms become painful or difficult to manage. Low mood and depression accounted for the third commonest symptom and this underscores the growing significance and increasing need for attention to mental health among medical students.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

We recommend the following;

1. Medical students should be taught early or reminded about the dangers of poor health seeking behaviour, especially the dangers of visiting the pharmacy for drugs without authorised prescription, antimicrobial resistance and presenting late.

2. The University of Uyo should establish a youth-friendly/counselling service centre closer to the medical students hostel and encourage those with low mood and depressive symptoms to seek help.
3. Collaborative research in medical schools across the country should be done to further explore the effects of several other factors on the health seeking behaviour of medical students.
4. Drug agencies and policy makers should ensure stricter access to over the counter medications. Only prescriptions from licensed health practitioners should be honoured.

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APPENDIX A

PARTICIPANT INFORMED CONSENT FORM

TITLE OF THE RESEARCH:Health Seeking Behaviour among Medical Students in the University of Uyo, Nigeria.

RESEARCHERS:SifonEkpa, Otihi Emmanuel, Nelson Udeme-Abasi, John Ebong, Etuk Raphael.

SPONSORS:The research is sponsored by the researchers.

PURPOSE OF THE RESEARCH:To determine the Health Seeking Behaviour of Medical Students in the University of Uyo.

PROCEDURE OF THE RESEARCH: You will be expected to fill a questionnaire regarding your health seeking behaviour and factors that influence them.

EXPECTED DURATION OF THE RESEARCH:We expect you to be involved in this research just for one day.

RISK:This study is not invasive and you would only be expected to fill a questionnaire. There are no other risks from participating in this study.

COST:Your participation in this study would cost you only a few minutes of your time.

BENEFITS:Information gotten from this study would add to the body of knowledge and help healthcare workers understand the factors influencing the health seeking behaviour of medical students with a view to improve their health.

CONFIDENTIALITY:All information obtained in this study will not be linked to you in any way. Your name or any method of identification will not be used in any publications or reports from this study.

VOLUNTARINESS:Your participation in this research is entirely voluntary.

CONSEQUENCES OF WITHDRAWAL:You can refuse to participate in this research, we would make efforts to comply to your wishes.

STATEMENT OF PARTICIPANTS: I have read and fully understand the description of the research and my participation is voluntary. I understand the purpose, methods, risks and benefits of the research to judge that I want to partake in it and I may freely stop being part of this study at any time.

.....
Signature of Researcher/Date

.....
Signature of Participant/Date

APPENDIX B

QUESTIONNAIRE

Health Seeking Behaviour Among Medical Students in the University of Uyo, Nigeria.

SECTION A *(tick only one option here)*

Sociodemographic Data

1. Gender Male Female
2. Age as at last birthday in years
3. Class/Level
 100 Level 200 Level 300 Level
 400 Level 500 Level (B) 500 Level (A)
 600 Level
4. Marital Status Single Married
 Divorced Widow/Widower
5. Religion Christian Islam Traditional
 Pentecostal
 Orthodox
 Others

SECTION B

Illness Experience in the Past 6 Months

1. Have you experienced any illness symptoms in the past 6 months?
 Yes No
2. If yes, please tick all applicable symptoms that you experienced in the past 6 months
 Fever Headache Chest Pain
 Cough Catarrh Abdominal Pain
 Joint pain Sore throat General body weakness
 Eye problems Boil Penile/Vaginal discharge
 Low mood/Depression Dental problems Waist Pain
 Breathlessness Others (pls specify)

SECTION C (*tick only one option here*)

Illness Response in the Past 6 Months

1. What was your (most) usual response to the illness(es) you experienced? (**Choose one option only**)

- Rest and did nothing about it
- Took herbal medications/concoctions/mixtures
- Went to the pharmacy/chemist to get some drugs
- Browsed the internet to manage the illness myself
- Consulted a colleague to seek advice on treatment regimen
- Used spiritual tools (praying, fasting, called a faith leader etc.)
- Visited the hospital at once

2. Did you eventually visit the hospital for your illness?

- Yes No

3. If Yes to the above, when did you decide to visit the hospital for your illness?

- I do random visits to the hospital even without symptoms
- Immediately the symptoms appeared
- When the discomfort/pain became unbearable
- When it affected my ability to cope academically
- When it became difficult to appear in public
- When someone with similar illness died
- I was persuaded by family/colleagues to visit the hospital

SECTION D (*choose all that apply in each section*)

Factors affecting choice of illness behaviour

If you took any of the following actions, what was your reason? (*Select all as applicable*)

1. Rest and did nothing (choose all that apply in this section)

- The illness was minor
- Previous experience which resolved without intervention

2. Took herbal medications/concoctions/mixtures
- Cultural disposition Easily accessible Saves Time
- More effective Cheaper Others.....
3. Went to the pharmacy/chemist to get drugs
- Easily Accessible Worked for a friend with similar symptoms
- Cheaper Others.....
4. Browsed the internet to manage the illness myself
- Easily Accessible Cheaper Saves Time
- Confidential/Private Has worked for me previously
- Others.....
5. Sought advice from a colleague to manage the illness
- Easily Accessible Cheaper Saves Time
- I trust my colleague Colleague is more experienced
- Others.....
6. Used spiritual tools
- I believe there is no cure Against my belief to seek medical help
- Cheaper Accessible Effective
- Others.....
7. Visited the hospital at once
- Easily Accessible Effective Time Saving
- I believe the symptoms are major Cheaper
- Competence of health workers Others.....